

ARTISTIC TRANSLATION: BRIDGING CULTURES THROUGH CREATIVITY

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Annotation: Art of artistic translation. Ethics and professionalism of translation. Aspects to pay attention to in the process of translation.

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Translation is often thought of as a straightforward linguistic task — the process of converting words from one language to another. However, in the realm of artistic translation, the process is far more complex, nuanced, and creative. Artistic translation goes beyond words to encompass a wide range of forms, from literature and theater to visual arts, music, and even dance. It is a creative endeavor that involves interpreting not just the meaning of a work, but also its emotional resonance, aesthetic value, and cultural context. In this article, we will explore the nature of artistic translation, the challenges it presents, and the profound role it plays in connecting cultures across the globe. Artistic translation is the act of transferring an artistic work — whether a novel, a poem, a play, a painting, or a piece of music — from one language or medium to another. Unlike technical translation, which focuses on the accuracy of transferring meaning, artistic translation requires a more interpretative approach. The goal is not merely to convey the original message but to preserve the artistic essence, emotional depth, and aesthetic qualities of the work in a new language or medium.

For example, a poet translating their work into another language faces the challenge of maintaining the original rhythm, rhyme, and metaphorical richness.

Similarly, when a novel is adapted into a screenplay, the translator must find a way to translate the emotional impact of the book’s prose into the visual language of film. In all cases, artistic translation involves a balance between faithfulness to the original and creative interpretations. Artistic translation manifests in many forms, each with its own set of challenges and methods. Below are some of the most common types of artistic translation: Literary translation is one of the most well-known forms of artistic translation. It involves translating novels, poems, short stories, and other literary works into a new language. Here, the translator must be attuned to the author’s style, tone, and intent. In some cases, literary translation can mean the difference between a book’s success or failure in the target language market. A good translation should evoke the same emotions and experiences as the original, even though it might need to adapt certain phrases or cultural references.

Theatrical translation involves adapting plays, musicals, or dramatic performances from one language and culture to another. This type of translation must account for the performative nature. Translating involves responsibility and making decisions, just like any other profession. That’s the reason why translation ethics show up. In particular, translation ethics are the principles as a guideline for professional translators and interpreters.

Ethics in translation is all about doing the right thing when translating words from one language to another. It's like being a good translator detective who not only finds the right words but also makes sure they're fair, honest, and respectful. Just as in our everyday lives, where we want to be kind and fair to others, translators also have a duty to be fair and true to the words they translate.

In this simple guide, you’ll explore the important rules and principles that help translators make good choices.

What are the Ethics in Translation? Here are some fundamental translation ethics below: (Note that there may be some variation in ethical considerations depending on the specific context and professional associations.)

Accuracy

Accuracy involves the original text's content, meaning, and intention. Translators' duty is to provide accurate translations. Their main goal should be conveying nuances and cultural references as accurately as possible.

Suppose you have an English menu at a restaurant, and it describes a dish as "grilled chicken." If the translator mistakenly translates it as "fried chicken" in the other language, it would be an inaccurate translation. Grilled chicken and fried chicken are two different ways of cooking chicken.

However, the customers might order something they didn't want if the translation isn't accurate.

1. Neutrality

Translators should refrain from adding their personal opinions, biases, or interpretations into the translation. The tone and style of the original text must be accurately reproduced by the translator. Hence, neutrality helps ensure that people who read the translation get an accurate understanding of the source text.

2. Confidentiality

Data privacy and confidentiality are also ethical obligations for translators. Translators are obligated to maintain the confidentiality of the materials they translate. They are also obligated not to reveal any confidential or sensitive information.

Suppose you are a translator working for a medical clinic. However, you need to translate a patient's medical records. In this situation, you must not share or discuss the patient's medical information with anyone who doesn't have a legitimate need to know. You should also take measures to ensure the security of the translation file and any related documents. For example, you can use methods like password protection.

Cultural Sensitivity

Dealing with sensitive or controversial subjects requires cultural awareness. That's why translators must be culturally sensitive and aware of cultural differences. They should adapt the translation to the target culture while respecting the source culture's values and norms.

For example, when translating a children's storybook, the translator should maintain cultural factors. Let's say, in the original story, there's a scene where characters celebrate a holiday specific to their culture, such as Chinese New Year. In this situation, the translator should ensure that the holiday is accurately represented in the new language. The translator should also ensure using appropriate terminology and customs that are relevant to the target culture. If the story is translated for an audience in the United States it can be translated as Thanksgiving to make it relatable to American readers.

5. Transparency

Translators should be transparent with clients about their qualifications and limitations. Translation is a wide field which has subfields. Translators are trained by a specific area they have chosen such as medicine, law and technical. If a translator is not proficient in a particular subject matter or language pair, they should decline the assignment. Seeking help from a more qualified colleague can be another solution for this situation.[3]

Let's say you're a translator working with a client who needs a legal document translated. You have the necessary language skills for the task. However, this legal document involves a highly specialised area of law that you're not familiar with, such as international maritime law. In this situation, it's essential to be transparent with your client.

You should inform them about your expertise and limitations. Being transparent about your qualifications ensures that the translation is of the highest quality possible. Transparency is important in building trust and maintaining professional integrity in translation work. of theater, which relies not only on dialogue but also on timing, gestures, and audience reaction. Theatrical translation may include subtitling for film or television, or even live performances, where the translator must find ways to adapt humor, cultural references, and local idioms so that they resonate with a new audience. In the visual arts, translation refers to the reinterpretation of an artwork through a different medium or within a new cultural context. This could involve transforming a painting into a piece of digital art, adapting a famous sculpture for

modern sensibilities, or even creating new artwork that responds to the cultural themes of the original piece. Visual arts translation often requires the artist to consider how their medium interacts with cultural and aesthetic differences in the target audience.

Film adaptations, music translations, and other multimedia translations involve bringing a creative work to life in a different cultural or linguistic environment.

That's the conclusion, artistic translation helps preserve and adapt cultural heritage.

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